

Synthesis and Characterisation of Monochloro- and Dichlorothiophenoxides of Arsenic(III)

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In the past few years there has been a spate of discoveries of a wide variety of metal thiolates¹ with fascinating structural complexity². Different synthetic routes have been employed for incorporation of thiolate into transition metal complexes¹. In spite of much of the recent development of metal thiolate chemistry particularly the pioneering research by Holm³, a few scattered reports are available about the synthesis of arsenic thiolates^{4,5}. In one of our recent communication⁶, we have reported an improved method of synthesis of $\text{As}(\text{SC}_6\text{H}_5)_3$. Here it is our intention to put forth a relatively simple method of syntheses of new monochloro- and dichlorothiophenolates of arsenic(III) using $\text{As}(\text{SC}_6\text{H}_5)_3$ and AsCl_3 which is attractive because of the ease of isolation of the compounds without giving any by-product.

Results and Discussion

Formation of monochlorodithiopheno- and dichloromonothiophenoarsenic(III), may be rationalised in terms of the following reactions :

Although the above reactions are slightly exothermic at room temperature but the components had to be refluxed for about 24 h to complete the reaction. These compounds are fairly stable

and can be stored for a longer period without decomposition. They are soluble in most of the organic solvents. Molar conductance values of millimolar solutions of these compounds in nitrobenzene is too low ($1.36\text{--}2.02 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) to be attributed to an electrolyte while molecular weight determination in the same solvent suggests that they exist as monomers in this solvent.

The results of ^1H nmr spectra of $\text{AsCl}_2(\text{SC}_6\text{H}_5)$ and $\text{AsCl}(\text{SC}_6\text{H}_5)_2$ are quite interesting. ^1H nmr data of compounds has been compared with the spectra of free thiophenol. The spectra of pure thiophenol exhibit a single sharp signal at δ 7.34 (ArH). This signal splits into two sharp resonance in both the compounds. The signal appearing at δ 7.4–7.5 (*ortho* protons) shows a significant downfield shift on compound formation. However the signal at δ 7.3–7.32 (*meta* and *para* protons) indicates that these remain unaltered on complexation. Confirmation of the stoichiometry of the compounds has been observed from a comparison of the integrated intensities of the aromatic protons. Ir spectra of these compounds, especially in the lower region, have been helpful to confirm the formation of these compounds. Apart from the bands at 486, 396, 378 and 490, 402 and 368 cm^{-1} in $\text{AsCl}(\text{SC}_6\text{H}_5)_2$ and $\text{AsCl}_2(\text{SC}_6\text{H}_5)$ assigned to $\nu_{\text{As-S}}$, sharp bands at 420–430 cm^{-1} may be assigned to $\nu_{\text{As-Cl}}$ modes⁶. Other significant bands around 740–750 and 680–690 cm^{-1} assigned to $\nu_{\text{As-S-C}}$ are in agreement with the earlier reports⁷.

The weak Lewis acid character of trihalides of group-V elements has prompted us to explore the reactivity of the isolated compounds with nitrogenous bases. Addition compounds of composition $\text{AsCl}_n(\text{SC}_6\text{H}_5)_{3-n} \cdot 2\text{L}$ and $\text{AsCl}_n(\text{SC}_6\text{H}_5)_{3-n} \cdot \text{B}$ ($n = 1, 2$; L = monodentate amine; B = bidentate 2,2'-bipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline) have been obtained on reacting the compounds with different nitrogenous bases (Table 1). They are non-electrolytes and exists as monomers in nitrobenzene as indicated by analytical data.

In the ir spectra of the addition compounds with different amines the most significant changes observed are those due to ν_{NH} , $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ and H-N-C deformation modes. The trends in shifting of these bands on coordination with arsenic are in agreement with those reported earlier⁸. The spectra of 2,2'-bipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline adducts show similar frequency shifts. Positive shifts have been observed for vibrations involving the carbon ring skeleton in out-of-plane or in-plane distortion in carbon-carbon bond stretching, while negative shifts have been observed for vibrations involving carbon-hydrogen bonds. These shifts are suggestive of coordination of ligand through both the nitrogen atoms⁹. Further, the new bands

in the region 500–510 cm^{-1} in all the adducts may be tentatively assigned to $\nu_{\text{As-N}}$ modes¹⁰. Based on the results, it is proposed that these adducts have a trigonal bipyramidal arrangement around arsenic.

Experimental

Arsenic trithiophenoxide was prepared by the reported method⁵. Arsenic trichloride was used after distillation. The organic solvents and nitrogenous bases used in the present study were purified by standard methods. Arsenic was quantitatively estimated by potassium iodate method while chlorine by Volhard's method.

Ir spectra (KBr/nujol) were recorded on a Beckmann spectrophotometer, and ¹H nmr spectra on a JNM-PMX6S1 spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard. Molecular weight was determined cryoscopically in nitrobenzene. Conductance was measured on an Elico conductivity bridge.

Monochlorodithiopheno- and dichloromonothiophenoarsenic(III) were prepared by reacting arsenic trithiophenoxide with arsenic trichloride in 2 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar ratios respectively,

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND IR SPECTRAL (cm^{-1}) DATA OF ADDITION COMPOUNDS OF $\text{AsCl}(\text{SC}_6\text{H}_5)_2$ AND $\text{AsCl}_2(\text{SC}_6\text{H}_5)$ WITH ALIPHATIC AMINES AND NITROGENOUS BASES

Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(calcd.)				Λ_M $\Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^2\text{mol}^{-1}$	Mol.wt. Found / (Calcd.)	ν_{NH}	$\nu_{\text{C-N}}$	$\nu_{\text{As-Cl}}$	$\nu_{\text{As-N}}$
	As	Cl	C	H						
$\text{AsCl}_2(\text{SC}_6\text{H}_5) \cdot 2\text{BuNH}_2$	18.73 (18.7)	17.66 (17.70)	41.75 (41.89)	5.44 (5.25)	2.1	396 (401)	3 368	1 040	421	510
$\text{AsCl}_2(\text{SC}_6\text{H}_5) \cdot 2\text{Et}_3\text{N}$	17.20 (16.37)	15.54 (15.50)	46.98 (47.16)	7.77 (7.64)	2.3	436 (458)	3 384	1 038	428	514
$\text{AsCl}_2(\text{SC}_6\text{H}_5) \cdot 1,10\text{-phen}$	16.77 (17.24)	16.29 (16.32)	49.51 (49.65)	2.89 (2.98)	1.7	447 (435)	—	1 024	440	496
$\text{AsCl}_2(\text{SC}_6\text{H}_5) \cdot 2,2'\text{-bipy}$	19.43 (18.24)	17.19 (17.27)	46.82 (46.71)	2.95 (3.16)	1.62	386 (411)	—	1 021	430	489
$\text{AsCl}(\text{SC}_6\text{H}_5)_2 \cdot 2\text{BuNH}_2$	16.19 (15.82)	7.66 (7.49)	50.39 (50.63)	5.39 (5.48)	2.03	463 (474)	3 414	1 026	419	496
$\text{AsCl}(\text{SC}_6\text{H}_5)_2 \cdot 2\text{-Et}_3\text{N}$	14.7 (14.15)	6.96 (6.69)	54.09 (54.33)	7.29 (7.54)	1.7	510 (530)	3 381	1 160	427	512
$\text{AsCl}(\text{SC}_6\text{H}_5)_2 \cdot 1,10\text{-Phen}$	13.99 (14.76)	6.62 (6.98)	56.51 (56.69)	3.49 (3.54)	2.5	536 (508)	—	1 035	426	491
$\text{AsCl}(\text{SC}_6\text{H}_5)_2 \cdot 2,2'\text{-bipy}$	14.88 (15.49)	7.04 (7.33)	54.47 (54.54)	3.64 (3.71)	3.24	504 (484)	—	1 120	426	504

NOTE

in dry benzene under reflux for about 24 h. The former compound of composition $\text{AsCl}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{S})_2$ was isolated as white solid while the latter $\text{AsCl}_2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{S})$ as colourless liquid by concentrating the resulting clear solutions. The products so obtained were purified by recrystallisation and distillation respectively : $\text{AsCl}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{S})_2$, white solid, m.p. 98° (Found : As, 22.2; Cl, 9.9. Calcd. for : As, 22.8; Cl, 10.2%); $\text{AsCl}_2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{S})$, colourless oily liquid, b.p. 130° (Found : As, 36.9; Cl, 27.8. Calcd. for : As, 37.5; Cl, 27.3%).

Addition compounds of thiophenoxides of arsenic(III) were prepared by reacting $\text{AsCl}_n(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{S})_{3-n}$ ($n = 1, 2$) with monodentate and bidentate nitrogenous bases in approximately 1 : 2 and 1 : 1 molar ratios at room temperature in benzene. The mixture was continuously stirred for about 8 h when solid compounds separated out which were filtered and dried under reduced pressure.

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